

Testing a DOI

Version 3

13:50

It looks like when we initially create a record, it gets a number N and then there are two DOIs associated with it:

```
zenodo.N <- version 1  
zenodo.N-1 <- points to all versions
```

then if I we ask for a new version, it gets a new record number Y, and then mints just one URL:

```
zenodo.Y <- version 2
```

but in this case zenodo.Y-1 does not seem to be minted.

So for this version we just have <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3865937>

Version 2

13:38

It seems the DOIs went live immediately...

The “reserve DOI” already reserved a new DOI

version 2: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3865920>

with a document id. <https://zenodo.org/deposit/3865920>

which begs the question of what the prev record might point to: <https://zenodo.org/deposit/3865919>

Version 1

This has the zenodo record 3865903 to the DOI should be

version 1: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3865903>

all versions: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3865902> (guessing it is one less than the record number)

Time of upload: 13:26 [2020-05-30 Sat]

Compiling this document

```
rmarkdown::render('doitest.Rmd', output_format='pdf_document')
```